

STUDY OF BRAID TOPOLOGY AND EFFECT OF BRAID PATTERN ON COMPOSITE PROPERTIES

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1 Introduction

Braiding is the formation of the bias interlacement of three or more strands of material. Conventional braiding machines adopt the maypole arrangement with half the yarn carriers rotating in a clockwise direction and the other half in an anti-clockwise direction along a circular track whilst interlacing with each other. The circular braiding machine forms a tubular structure which either creates a continuous sleeve or gets deposited on a mandrel [1, 2].

Braided structures are similar to woven structures in terms of their pattern of yarn interlacement. For braiding this is called the “braid pattern” and most common braid structure is regular braids which has a similar pattern to a 2/2 twill weaves but in the bias direction (figure 1).

Fig. 1. The regular braid structure

The second most common is the Diamond braid structure. This is similar to a 1/1 plain weave pattern but in the bias direction (figure 2). The arrangement of yarns is referred to as the topology. Braids can either be flat or more commonly produced in a tubular form, only a few inches in diameter due to a

limited number of yarns used, where as woven fabrics are often produced as a broad cloth, several-metres wide.

Fig. 2. The diamond braid structure

Traditionally braiding was used to produce narrow fabrics such as ropes and shoelaces. In recent years technical applications in composite materials are becoming popular. The structures are significantly larger, therefore require larger braiding machines. Advances in the size of the circular braiding machine, sees the continuous increase in the number of yarn carriers the machine holds and therefore an increase in the braid pattern variations which can be produced. This makes it even more important to be able to analyze the braid topology prior to braiding the material. Predicting the braid topology allows the analysis of yarn interlacements and braid structure. This effects downtime, labour and cost by reducing trial and error methods of producing different braid patterns.

These two sets of braid yarns interlace with each other at a bias angle to the machine axis. This angle of interlacement is called the braid angle (θ) shown in figure 3. The braid angle achieved is dependent

on the braiding machine parameters; the braid-head speed and the take-up speed which can be controlled and modified as per the requirements.

Fig. 3. The braid angle [3]

A broad range of studies have been conducted previously on braiding, braid geometries, and braid structures [4-8], however braid topology and its effect on the braid properties is still an area for extensive research.

2 Braid topology

By studying the movements of the yarn carriers and by taking into account the bobbin arrangements, the braid pattern can be composed (figure 4). This is achieved by initially numbering the bobbins going in each direction. The example given is based on a 12 horngear circular braiding machine, which has a 1:2 horngear to bobbin ratio, therefore giving 24 potential positions to house a bobbin (12 clockwise and 12 anti-clockwise). In the topology diagram the bobbins moving in the clockwise direction are represented in white and the bobbins moving in the anti-clockwise direction are in grey. As the bobbins complete their rotations they go over and under the bobbins moving in the opposite direction, this deposits the yarn under and over these yarns. Depending on which yarn is on the surface of the braid, this yarn is shown in the braid pattern. Conventional horngear braiding machine, when fully loaded with bobbins, this will produce a regular braid.

If a bobbin is removed from the machine, this removes the interlacement of that yarn through the braid pattern [9]. One or several bobbins can be removed. This creates braids with significantly different structures and hence geometries. These geometries can be analyzed and compared; they produce not only aesthetically different braids but also mechanically variable performing materials.

Fig. 4. Developing a braid pattern for a 12 horngear machine (a) numbering braid bobbins; (b) braid pattern.

Removing bobbins from a braiding machine allows structures of smaller diameters to be braided over without using time and resources to load the entire machine. Examples of topology based on a 12 horngear machine but using various numbers of bobbins is represented in figure 5. The size of the braid pattern is proportionate to the number of braid bobbins used.

Fig. 5. The braid topology using different number of yarns on a 12 horngear braiding machine

By being able to map the yarn topology it allows the operator to see the braid structure prior to braiding. This is essential as the braid structure and interlacement have an effect on the braids physical and mechanical properties. The lower the number of yarn carriers utilised, the fewer the yarn interlacements. This increases the number of straight floats of yarns and therefore reduces the level of crimp. Lower crimp is ideal for high performance

materials such as Carbon tow, whose mechanical properties are at their optimum at zero crimp. With certain braid topology structures it is possible to get a preform with zero interlacement, zero crimp and near-to-zero waviness (dependent on the tow cross-section placed in the opposite direction).

2.1 Theoretical topology simulation vs. actual samples

The theoretical topology simulation can be compared with actual samples in order to verify the braid pattern. Choosing to use less number of braid yarns reduced the width of a braid, however if the mandrel is used then the width of the braid will stay the same but effect other geometrical parameters such as tow spacing and number of interlacement points. Figure 6 shows theoretical representations of the braid pattern or braids produced over a constant mandrel diameter using a varying number of braid yarns. The numbers of bobbins are 4, 8, 12, 16, 20 and 24. Actual samples were produced using Glassfibre as yarn moving in the clockwise direction and Carbon fibre representing braid bobbins moving in the anti-clockwise direction. These different tows have been used so the yarn patterns and interlacements can easily be visualised.

Fig. 6. The interlacement patterns of various numbers of braid bobbins

Braids which use the same number of braid yarns, but have different braid structures also exhibit different properties. Figure 7 represents the cross-

section structure of a regular braid and a diamond braid along the fibre axis for the same number of yarns. By varying the braid structure, this also has an effect on the braid geometry such as tow width, tow spacing and tow thickness.

Fig. 7. Cross-section view of braid along the fibre axis

3 Experimental Methodology

A regular braid and a diamond braid samples were produced using the circular braiding machines and braiding over a 25mm diameter metal mandrel. The regular braid was produced using a 12 horngear machine with a total of 24 yarn carriers. All 24 yarn carriers were occupied to produce a regular 2/2 braid. The diamond braid was produced using a 24 horngear machine which houses a total of 48 yarn carriers but only 24 yarn carriers were utilized (figure 8), where for each direction every alternative yarn carrier was left empty in order to produce a diamond 1/1 structure using 24 bobbins in total. Therefore, both samples use 12 carriers rotating in the clockwise direction and 12 in the anticlockwise direction. The number of yarns has been kept constant and the braid angle has also been kept constant at a 45°. The variable is the braid structure.

The two sets of regular and diamond braid samples were produced in tubular shape and in single layer. Braiding was carried-out to produce a tri-axial braid structure embedding six axial carbon tows those were placed equidistantly. These axial tows were removed followed by braiding to facilitate removal of the braid sleeve from the core tool. In order to prevent the samples being distorted in the further processing, cello tape was placed along the length of each braid sample to secure the fibre orientation. The axial yarns were removed from the structure which reduced the grip of the interlaced helix fibre to the mandrel. The samples were then removed

from the core and placed onto a tool plate. With the aid of another plate which applied an approximate force of 14 N, the samples were flattened.

Fig. 8. A 24 Horngear machine house 24 out of 48 possible bobbins

3.1 Manufacture of composite laminate

Following the flattening, the samples were prepared for vacuum assisted resin infusion process. The flat samples were placed next to each other on to a tool plate and the open edges were secured. Layers of peel ply, perforated film and breather material was laid on top of the samples. The resin distribution tube (RDT) was placed along the length of a single braid instead of next to the width of multiple specimens on the tool plate (figure 9). This arrangement ensured wetting the samples individually as the resin flows. The vacuum distribution line was placed next to the last sample on the tool plate. The whole arrangement was covered with bagging film, the edges of which were closed using sealant tape to provide an airtight seal onto the tool surface. In between the vacuum line laid inside the bag and the valve connected to the pump, a resin trap was placed to help absorb excess resin during curing. As the air was evacuated, the inlet tube was opened in a controlled manner; as a result the resin flew through the RDT. The braid samples were impregnated using a mixture of epoxy resin (Araldite LY564) and hardener (XB3486) with a resin to hardener mixing ratio of 100:34. After the resin infusion was completed, the part was cured in an oven at 80°C for 8 hours. Followed by curing, the

composite samples were cooled down slowly before removing from the bagging assembly.

Fig. 9. Preform infusion set-up

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Geometrical Analysis of dry preform

The geometrical measurements of the braid preform have been assessed both on the mandrel, off the mandrel after flattening along with the composite coupon. A summary of these results are given in table 1. Immediately after braiding the tow width of the regular braid was 3.95mm as compared to 3.32mm for the diamond braid, however when the samples were flattened the tow width was found to have increased to 4.58 and 3.53mm for regular and diamond braids respectively. Furthermore after producing the composite coupons, the tow width further increased to 5.24mm for the regular and 4.01mm for the diamond braid.

The thickness of the braid is influenced by the number of braid yarns used, the thickness of the yarns/tows, alongside other factors. The tow thickness of the initial braid was calculated on the mandrel by using the diameter of the braided sleeve, against the mandrel diameter. The total circumference of the braid was measure from which the diameter was calculated and therefore a single layer thickness. A single layer contains 2 tows so is divided by 2 to get a single tow thickness. For the regular braid the tow thickness is 0.38mm compared to 0.57mm for the diamond braid. The thickness of the flattened braid was not able to be measured due to the compressive behaviour of the tows. The

thickness of the tows within the composite coupon can be measured by cutting and polishing a sample along the fibre axis and taking microscopic images. Using an image analysis software the thickness is measured. The thickness of the tows within the specimens was 0.25 and 0.36mm for the regular and diamond respectively. The tow width of a braid changes during the transition of a braid straight after braiding, after flattening and after infusion.

In addition to the tow parameters, the tow spacing can also be observed for the different structures. The tow spacing for a regular braid was seen to be 0.46mm on the mandrel, 0.55mm after flattening and 0.78mm after infusion. For the diamond sample the tow spacing was 4.53mm on the mandrel, 4.76mm after flattening and 5mm after infusion. Also the crimp of the sample was calculated by using the cross-section image along the fibre axis. The crimp for the regular braid composite sample was 0.17% compared to 0.34% for the diamond sample.

		Regular (2/2)	Diamond (1/1)
Tow width (mm)	On Mandrel	3.95	3.32
	Flattened	4.58	3.53
	Composite	4.77	4.01
Tow thickness (mm)	On Mandrel	0.38	0.57
	Composite	0.25	0.36
Tow Spacing (mm)	On Mandrel	4.46	4.53
	Flattened	4.55	4.76
	Composite	4.78	5.00
Crimp in composite (%)		0.17	0.34
Fibre volume fraction		0.52	0.46

Table 1. A summary of the geometrical analysis for regular and diamond braid samples off mandrel, after flattening and in composite state.

Calculating the fibre volume fraction involved acid digestion of the composite matrix and measuring the volume of fibre in a sample against the complete volume of the composite sample. The ASTM Standard D3171 [10] was used to calculate the fibre

volume fractions of both diamond (1/1) and regular (2/2) braided coupons. The fibre volume fraction value of 0.52 was observed for regular braid whilst, a value of 0.46 was observed for diamond braid

4.2 Mechanical Testing

Tensile testing of the braided composite coupons has been conducting using the Instron 5982. The coupon for testing is marked (figure 10) and a visual extensometer is used, which detects these markings and measures the axial stress.

Fig. 10. Marked coupon in testing rig

During testing the coupon exhibits a necking behaviour due to the shearing of the tows [11]. This necking behaviour is shown in figure 9. The typical stress-strain behaviour of the regular and diamond coupons are shown in figure 11 and a summary of the tensile results are given in table 2. The initial modulus for both samples were similar however the maximum stress and maximum strain values vary greatly. The regular braid exhibits stress value of 133.54MPa compared to 163.27MPa for the diamond sample and a strain value of 0.05 compared to 0.07.

Fig. 11. Regular coupon (a) before and (b) after testing; Diamond coupon (c) before and (d) after testing

Fig. 11. Typical stress-strain behavior of regular and diamond braided coupons

	Regular (2/2)	Diamond (1/1)
Maximum Stress (MPa)	133.54±10.59	163.27±6.49
Maximum Strain	0.05±0.029	0.07±0.027
Modulus (GPa)	14.4±0.94	14.4±0.85

Table 2. The average maximum stress, maximum strain and modulus values for a regular braided and diamond braided coupon.

5 Conclusions

The braid geometry and physical properties are influenced by the braid topology and can be predicted using braid topology models. The general rules can be applied to any braiding machine regardless of how many yarn carriers it holds. It is possible to produce braided sleeve preforms with different braid structures but using the same number of braid tows/yarns. This is achieved by using a certain selection of bobbins of various size or braid machines.

The geometry of the dry braid preform sample was analysed and compared for the regular and diamond braids. An increase in tow width of the regular and diamond samples was seen after flattening and resin infusion, where tow width of regular braid was higher width than diamond braid. The tow spacing also increased slightly in each of the structures between the initial braid, after flattening and in the composite. In addition to the difference in tow width, there is a reduction of the tow thickness between the initial braid on the mandrel and in the composite, where the diamond braid had higher tow thickness in both states than the regular braided samples.

The diamond (1/1) sample had a higher crimp percentage than the regular (2/2) braid samples. This is expected due the nature of the structure of interlacements where the regular braid has longer floats than the diamond structure. However it was observed that the regular braided samples had higher fibre volume fraction compared to the diamond braid.

When under load the braided coupon exhibits a necking behavior. The young's modulus for both regular and diamond braided composite samples were found to be the same however the failure strengths of the samples differed greatly. The diamond (1/1) braided coupons exhibit higher failure stress and strain compared to regular (2/2).

References

- [1] Potluri, P. Braiding. *International encyclopedia of composites*. ed Nicolais, L. Wiley: New York. 2012
- [2] Horrocks, A.R., ed. *Handbook of Technical Textiles*. 2000.
- [3] Potluri, P., Nawaz, S., Developments in braided fabric.. *Specialist yarn and fabric structures: Developments and*

applications. ed. Gong, R.H., Woodhead Publishing. 333-353. 2011

[4] Brunnschweiler, D., Braids and Braiding. *Journal of the Textile Institute Proceedings*, 44(9): p. 666 - 686. 1953

[5] Douglass, W.A., *Braiding and Braiding machinery*: Centrex Publishing Company. 1969

[6] Ko, F.K., C.M. Pastore, and A.A. Head, *Atkins & Pearce handbook of industrial braiding*. 1989.

[7] Lyons, J. and C. Pastore, *Effect of braid structure on yarn cross-sectional shape*. *Fibers and Polymers*. 5(3): p. 182-186. 2004

[8] Potluri, P. Recent Advances in 3D Textile Composites. in *ICERP. IIT Madras*. 2002

[9] Ravenhorst van, J.H. and R. Akkerman, A spool pattern tool for circular braiding, *18th International Conference on Composite Materials, ICCM: Jeju Island, Korea*. 2011

[10] ASTM Standard D3171-99,, *Standard Test Methods for Constituent Content of Composite Materials*.

[11] Hatsukade, Y., et al., Nondestructive evaluation of $\pm 45^\circ$ flat-braided carbon-fiber-reinforced polymers with carbon nanofibers using HTS-SQUID gradiometer. *Physica C: Superconductivity*, 484(0): p. 195-201. 2013